

The Role of Model Perspective in Addressing the Management of Cattle Rustling Among Pastoral Communities in Kenya

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Abstract: The study focused on the effect of policies deployed by individual personalities (role models) in the management of cattle rustling in Kenya. The area under study was North Western, Kenya which comprised five counties; Elgeiyo Marakwet, West Pokot, Turkana, Samburu and Baringo which had a total population of 2,980,035 persons vide the Kenya National Population census of 2019. The sample size was 444, determined by Krejcie R.V and Morgan D.W table of 1990. The findings indicated that the community role models had a positive contribution in respect to the management of cattle rustling was concerned. The evidence was made through the exposition of mean scores such as, the efforts contributed to restriction of cattle rustling by role models with a mean score of 1.6, improved school attend by 1.7, re-introduction of farming as an alternative source of livelihood by 1.4; provision of market to readily produced goods by 2.6 and discouraging of killing of people in raids by 2.1. It is concluded that role models championed peaceful co-existence among all the North Rift communities and preached peace, encouraged people to take up alternative sources of livelihoods beside cattle rearing, changed people's mindsets through supporting education and provided opportunities through scholarships. The study recommends that the affected area role models should visit their community regularly to engage the local people on the importance of seeking alternative means of livelihood.

Keywords: Cattle rustling, role models/individual policies, interface, non-state policies, state based policies, pastoral communities.

I. INTRODUCTION

The cattle rustling menace remained one of the main socio-economic bottlenecks in respect to the attainment of live hoods in the world and more so among pastoral communities. (Sharkenskey, 2016). It is a form of crime which most Governments and security organizations in the world are grappling with including World-west, Canada, West African States South Africa and East Africa depict myriad of policy actions through legislators part in place to curb the vice. (Fwkayamo, 2013). In East Africa, the vice is predominantly in Eastern Uganda among the Karamojong people, Northern parts of Kenya and South Sudan. (Pelliseng, 2015). In the Northern parts of Kenya especially in the study area, there have been notable individual personalities who distinguished themselves and volunteered to deliberately contain the practice using various arenas among them sports and the biblical teachings. The notable portions were Tegla Lorupa (sports activities) and Bishop Cornelius Korir (biblical teachings). (Mkutu 2019).

Statement of the Problem

The citizens donate their powers to the government for protection and general security of their lives and property. Jean Jacques Rousseau, (1762) has works on sound contract theory was explained by modern scholars who have experienced the same by including issues of democratic governance principles. (Mkutu, 2019). Despite such authorities bequeathed to the government for governance, the property and lives of people have been lost especially because of the cattle rustling

practices. According to Bashir, (2017), states that besides loss of life and property, schools have been closed down, displacements of people from their homes, farms destroyed and socio-economic situations have relapsed to desolations and poverty engulfed the livestock farmers despite existence of the government, security agencies and other leaders in the community. As per Barilla.S, Plang I and Isaac, (2019), this situation necessitated the emergency of individual personnel who came to save the people.

Objective of the Study

To find out the effect of policies deployed by individual personalities in the management of cattle rustling in Kenya.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The study made reference to two schools of thought in the focus of explaining the role played by community personalities to address cattle rustling theories; Formal schooling and Underdevelopment. They pursued their socio-economic change through formal schooling and utilization of existing community opportunities to improve their livelihoods and shun pastoralism which had insecurity challenges. Their security into clarion call for change of attitude resonated well with several scholars and researchers among them Kratli, (2001) who believed that education transformed youth better than informal rearing of livestock, a practice which encouraged banditry and discourages a mechanism of cultural transformation. Through formal transformation of knowledge, Gumba (2020) echoed on the sports activities by Teglo as one of the ways that would transform the society and stubborn community and intercommunity raids. He underscored that Tegla had pacified the Uganda-Kenya border through Tegla Lorofe Foundation. Bishop Cornelliuss Korir supported education policy and its activities pf 100% transition primary to secondary up to University. He took an initiative to use his influence in the church to ask parents and teachers to embrace education and provided bursaries and other material support to less fortunate in society. (Kepron, 2013). He dymistified the notion held by local communities that the European based education interfere with the local culture where he explained that the two can co-exist without conflict-Local culture and formal education. Other interventions he made were peace-making in churches, outreaches (campaigns) and caring for the displaced persons due to raids. He further taught that the communities that dowry can be paid through other ways and not by use of livestock. He bridged the gap among waring communities in the North Rift because he commanded huge respect amongst leaders. (Obare, 2020).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To achieve the research objectives, the study preferred appropriate, unbiased, effective and economical approaches with an aim to maximize on reliability of data collected and achieved the smallest errors possible. The study took a descriptive research design which answered the and how questions as reflected in the hypotheses. This called for a mixed-method study design which invoked the usage of both qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection techniques. The study adopted inferential statistical analysis which made it possible to find critical relationships between variables for formidable generalization of findings to apply across the population in the North Rift. The area under study was North Western, Kenya which comprised five counties; Elgeiyo Marakwet, West Pokot, Turkana, Samburu and Baringo which had a total population of 2,980,035 persons vide the Kenya National Population census of 2019. The sample size was 444, determined by Krejcie R.V and Morgan D.W table of 1990.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Individual based policies

Findings on Individual based policies that influenced the management of cattle rustling indicated that community role models had positively contributed to reduction in cattle rustling as supported by a mean 1.5729 and a standard deviation .4953. A Sig. (2-tailed) .003 was derived. Community role models had positively contributed to school attendance as supported by a mean 1.7109 and a standard deviation .4539. A Sig. (2-tailed) .032 was derived. Community role models had positively contributed to reduction in cattle rustling as supported by a mean 1.4271 and a standard deviation .4953. A Sig. (2-tailed) .012 was derived. Community role models had positively contributed to adoption of farming as supported by a mean 1.4271 and a standard deviation .4953. A Sig. (2-tailed) .012 was derived. Cattle rustling can only be curbed through individual responsibility on maintaining peace. Suppose the citizens in that region focused on protecting their property, in that case, they should have been at the forefront of ensuring that the gaps within the national government and county government had been filled up. If the residents continued to assume the government initiatives of maintaining peace, then

cattle rustling would not be easily eradicated in the region. The mission of Tecla Loroupe Peace Foundation was to promote peaceful coexistence and socioeconomic development of poor and marginalized communities in the North Rift and the Horn of Africa. The Late Bishop Cornelius Korir made various interventions such as caring for the wounded victims and providing healing and reconciliation using the bottom-up approach. Community role models discouraged cattle rustling as supported by a mean 1.2813 and a standard deviation .4502. A Sig. (2-tailed) .024 was derived. Community role models gave scholarships as supported by a mean 1.2917 and a standard deviation .4551. A Sig. (2-tailed) .036 was derived. Community role models provided employment after school as supported by a mean 2.7188 and a standard deviation .4859. A Sig. (2-tailed) .022 was derived. Community role models supported locals by loans to own permanent structures as supported by a mean 3.1432 and a standard deviation .5642. A Sig. (2-tailed) .024 was derived. However, the respondents disagreed that community role models supported locals to own farm implements as supported by a mean 2.2786 and a standard deviation .0285. A Sig. (2-tailed) .211 was derived. Community role models offered education on good farming as supported by a mean 2.1380 and a standard deviation .3453. A Sig. (2-tailed) .022 was derived. Community role models offered locals markets for their produce as supported by a mean 2.5729 and a standard deviation .4953. A Sig. (2-tailed) .013 was derived. Community role models encouraged community intermarriages as supported by a mean 1.7083 and a standard deviation .4551. A Sig. (2-tailed) .012 was derived. Community role models taught against killing to acquire cattle as supported by a mean 2.1328 and a standard deviation .2413. A Sig. (2-tailed) .013 was derived. Community role models taught that cattle is not the only means of paying dowry as supported by a mean 1.4193 and a standard deviation .4940. A Sig. (2-tailed) .013 was derived. Community role models mitigated among communities as supported by a mean 1.5625 and a standard deviation .9003. A Sig. (2-tailed) .025 was derived. Community role models had increased in number in our region as supported by a mean 1.5703 and a standard deviation .4956. A Sig. (2-tailed) .033 was derived. The results from all the indicators of individual based policies indicated that there was statistical significance in the individual based policies that influenced cattle rustling ($p < 0.05$) out of the 16 descriptive statements. However, the respondents disagreed that community role models support locals to own farm implements and community role models taught that cattle was not the only means of paying dowry ($p > 0.05$). All the mean scores were above one (1) across all the descriptive statements which showed that there was variation in the causes of cattle rustling.

TABLE 1. Individual based policies

	N	M	SD	Sig
Community role models have positively contributed to reduction in cattle rustling	384	1.5729	.4953	.003
Community role models have positively contributed to school attendance	384	1.7109	.4539	.032
Community role models have positively contributed to reduction in cattle rustling	384	1.5729	.4953	.012
Community role models have positively contributed to adoption of farming	384	1.4271	.4953	.034
Community role models discourage cattle rustling	384	1.2813	.4502	.024
Community role models gives scholarships	384	1.2917	.4551	.036
Community role models provides employment after school	384	2.7188	.4859	.022
Community role models supports locals by loans to own permanent structures	384	3.1432	.5642	.024
Community role models support locals to own farm implements	384	2.2786	.0285	.211
Community role models offers education on good farming	384	2.1380	.3453	.022
Community role models offers locals market to their produce	384	2.5729	.4953	.013
Community role models encourages community intermarriages	384	1.7083	.4551	.012
Community role models teach against killing to acquire cattle	384	2.1328	.2413	.013
Community role models teaches that cattle is not the only means of paying dowry	384	1.4193	.4940	.013
Community role models mitigates among communities	384	1.5625	.9003	.025
Community role models have increased in number in our region	384	1.5703	.4956	.033

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

The findings on Individual based policies that influenced the management of cattle rustling were; Community role models had positively contributed to reduction in cattle, they had positively contributed to increase of school attendance, reduced cattle rustling, positively contributed to adoption of farming practices, curbed cattle rustling through advocating for individual responsibility on maintaining peace, discouraged cattle rustling, gave scholarships to learners, provided employment to school leavers, after school, provided loans to local people to own permanent structures, failed to support local people to own farm implements, succeeded in offering good farming education, offered market to local people and encouraged inter-communal marriages, contributed to providing education against killings over livestock and that there were other ways of paying dowry. This research work found out that in the North Rift Valley, there were individuals who had become community models and advocated for eradication of cattle rustling and the general thuggery associated with it. Their approaches had been through the church crusades, sports, mentorship programs, youth seminars, peace elders' engagements and women empowerment programs. One such personality is the 3,000 triple chase World Record Holder Tegla Loroupe who had instituted sports activities in the North Rift where the youth participated each year. She used sports activities to teach against cattle rustling which she called an outdated practices and retrogressively denoted dark times of the past. Another personality in the North Rift who preached against cattle rustling and its effects was the Late Bishop Cornelius Korir who got peace award recommendation on 30th October, 2017 by Late President Hon. Mwai Kibaki for promoting peaceful co-existence among communities and shunning cattle theft. These two leaders championed peaceful co-existence among all the North Rift communities and preached peace, encouraged people to take up alternative sources of livelihoods beside cattle rearing, changed people's mindsets through supporting education and provided opportunities through scholarships.

Conclusion

It is concluded that role models championed peaceful co-existence among all the North Rift communities and preached peace, encouraged people to take up alternative sources of livelihoods beside cattle rearing, changed people's mindsets through supporting education and provided opportunities through scholarships.

Recommendation

The study recommends that the affected area role models should visit their community regularly to engage the local people on the importance of seeking alternative means of livelihood. It is recommended that when people from the affected communities get to Nairobi and other big towns to acquire their university education, they should not stay in those urban areas and avoid visiting home regularly for fear of cattle rustling and its aftermath. They are supposed to visit their homes as an encouragement to the people at home that education is good than relying on cattle rustling for livelihood that can at most time cause injuries or even loss of life and so education is safer.

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